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A study on the problems of women in unorganised sector with special reference to agriculture

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Abstract

In earlier days women were confining to the four walls of houses and led a protected life. In the present modern society they have come out of the four walls and take part in all sorts of activities competing successfully with men. This has become possible because of the increase in women's education social and occupational mobility, legal safeguard, industrialization and urbanization. It has been proved globally that women have been performing exceedingly well in various fields such as education, administration, politics, sports, medicine, aeronautics, trade and industries and social work. Thus the workers in the unorganised sector in general are outside the purview of protective Labour Laws and Trade Union Organizations. In this context the condition of women who are exploited even in organized sector, is worse in the unorganised sector. Problems of unorganised workers in India have been increasing recently. A vast majority of India's working population is in the unorganised sector and is consequently unprotected. In India, informal sector or the unorganised sector plays a vital role in the employment and production front. Around 94 percent work force including agriculture, are in the unorganised of informal sector, whereas just 6 percent are in the organized of formal sector. According to Central Statistical Organization, "the unorganised sector includes all those un-incorporated enterprises, the household industries which are not regulated by any legislation and which do not maintain annual accounts or balance sheets.

Keywords: Financial analysis, Motaal's Comprehensive Test, Cement industries performance

Introduction

Women in the Unorganised Sector

A high proportion of working women in India is employed in the unorganised sector mainly in agriculture, livestock and forestry, working women are manifested in agricultural activities like land preparation, seed grading, sowing, dibbling, planting, irrigation, threshing, winnowing, storing, crops, feeding cattle, looking after milt animal and poultry etc. the nature of works in agriculture which the women laborers perform exposes them to particular health hazards. In various states especially in south India, rice transplanting is done primarily by women labourers perform exploded them to particular health hazards. In various states especially in south India, rice transplanting is done primarily by women laborers. This increases their susceptibility to a number of ailments such as intestinal and parasitic infections, arthritis, rheumatic joints, leech bites etc. It is observed that work participation in the unorganised sector has been an increasing trend. Immobility of labor is the greatest impediment of women labor that keeps them confined to low paying, irregular and local avenues of employment in unorganised sector. Ignorance, tradition-bound attitudes, lack of skill, seasonal nature of employment, heavy physical work of difficult types, lack of job security, long hours of work, lack of minimum facilities at the work place, ill-treatment and bondage are some of the features of the employment of women in unorganised sector.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the socio-economic condition of women in the agricultural sector.
2. To find out the employment status of women in different season and the alternative sources of employment.
3. To know the gender disparity and occupational health problems faced by women labour in agriculture.
4. To analyze the saving habits and level of satisfaction of women labour in the agriculture.

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- To offer suggestions to overcome the problems of agricultural labour.

Sampling Design

The researcher has selected the simple random sampling method. The researcher has chosen 150 respondents from Munanjipatti Panchayat for the research.

Collection of Data

The method used by the researcher was personal interview with the help of carefully prepared interview schedule. Personal interview conducted among 150 respondents in the selected area. Secondary data were collected from the published as well as the unpublished records.

Processing of Data

The raw data collected may not give enough meaning to the study. So after the collection of primary data, the researcher has thoroughly verified the collected data. Afterwards, the data were edited and coded. A master table had been prepared to sum up all the information contained in the questionnaire. With the help of the master table, the collected data are tabulated and analyzed by the researcher using simple statistical tools.

Statistics in Research

The role of statistics in research is to function as tool in designing research, analyzing its data and drawing conclusions there from. Most research studies result in a large volume of raw data which must be suitably reduced so that the same can be read easily and can be used for further analysis. Clearly the science of statistics cannot be ignored by any research worker, even though he may not have occasion to use statistical methods in all details and ramifications.

Percentages

The expression of data in terms of percentage is one of the simplest statistical devices used in the interpretation of business and economic activities. Percentages are useful chiefly for the purpose of aiding comparison. A per cent is the number of hundredth part.

$$\text{Percentage} = b_1 / b_0 * 100$$

Chi – Square test

The χ^2 test is one of the simplest and most widely used tests for arriving at significance of the difference between the observed frequencies and the expected frequencies obtained from some hypothetical universe.

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum (O - E)^2}{E}$$

O – Observed frequencies

E = Expected frequencies

Ranking Scale

Garret ranking methods are used to study and analyse the problems that are being faced by the consumers.

Weighted Average Score

Weighted average score is used to study and analyse the various suggestion for improving the Public Distribution System.

The formula for weighted average score is = $\frac{EWX}{WX}$

Computed Average Growth Rate

Limitations

- Since the unorganised women labours are uneducated the respondents were unable to answer the questions asked by the researcher.
- Only 150 respondents are interviewed so the inferences and conclusions drawn are based on the information given by the respondents.
- Some of the respondents did not act favorably.

Previous Theses

Saibal Kar, (2007) in his thesis work find the better prospect for agricultural exports and productivity should increase agricultural wage. However, they argue that such an outcome depends on the capital movement between the formal and informal manufacturing sectors. This is shown in a model that demonstrates a close link between agricultural and informal wage.

Analysis and Interpretations Nature of Occupation of the Respondents

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Permanent labour	-	-
Casual labour	135	90
Cultivators cum casual labour	15	10
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

The above table shows that only 90percentage of the sampled respondent are in the casual labour, 10% of the sample respondents are cultivators cum casual labour. None of them was working on permanent basis.

Season-Wise Employment of Women Labour

Season	No. of Days Employed	Average Days
Kharif	1770/150	12
Rabi	15650/150	104
Summer	1970/150	13

Source: primary data

There are three seasons of employment namely kharif, Rabi, Summer and major employment available in the Rabi season, where more jobs are available and more workers are employed in other seasons the average employment availability ranges from 10-15%.

Alternative Source of Employment

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	150	100
No	-	-
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

The above table shows that all the100% of the samples are already having the alternative sources of employment.

Reason for Non-Availability of Agriculture Work

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Due to rain	-	-
Due to drought	123	82
Due to non-availability of agriculture work	27	18
Others	-	-
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

The above table shows that the reason of non-availability of agriculture work for the respondents. It is observed from the table 4.30, because of the drought 82% of the sampled respondents are not having agriculture work and the remaining 18% are not having agriculture work because of the farming is not done.

Daily Wages

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Rs. 100-150	138	92
Rs.150-200	12	8
Rs.200-250	-	-
Rs.250 and above	-	-
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

It is observed from the table 4.20 about the daily wages received by the respondents. Majority of 92% of the respondents are receiving Rs.100-150 for a day, Rest of the 8% are receiving Rs. 150-200 for a day.

Reason for Selecting the Agriculture Labour

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Monetary need	52	34
Poor education	34	23
Traditional work	25	17
Others	39	26
Total	150	100

Source: primary data

Rank Given By the Respondents On The Basis Of Problems Faced By Them

S. No	Problems	Garret Mean Score	Rank
1.	Un favourable Climatic condition	61.87	I
2.	Continuous work without rest	55.49	II
3.	Work overload	48.61	III
4.	No provision of refreshment at workplace	34.27	IV
5.	Less payment	33.23	V

Respondents' Mode of Saving

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Bank	47	31
Post office	22	15
Insurance policy	34	23
Others	20	13
Total	123	100

Table Showing Age and Level of Satisfaction

Level of Satisfaction / Age	Up to 30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years	61 years and above	Total
Yes	5	4	12	8	7	36
No	3	46	28	32	5	114
Total	8	50	40	40	12	150

H₀ There is no significant association between age and level of satisfaction.

H₁ There is significant association between age and level of satisfaction.

Source: primary data

X=17.321

d f= 4

p= 0.002

p<= 0.05 significant

The above table observed value of chi-square is 17.321 and the corresponding significance value is 0.002 which is less than 0.05, there is a significant between age and level of satisfaction. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Findings

- Most of the respondents are in the age group between 31-40 and followed by that 24.67% of the respondents are in the age group between 51-60.
- Most (46.76%) of the respondents are illiterate and followed by that 36% of the respondents can read and write.
- Most of the respondents are having 11-20 years of agriculture related experience.
- Majority (90%) of the respondents are the casual labour.
- Maximum number of respondents get job during Rabi season.
- Majority of 83% respondents, weeding job available in the summer season.
- Majority of 66% respondents, transplanting job is available in the rainy season.
- All the respondents are having the alternative sources of employment.
- Most (91%) of the respondents are in the National Rural Employment Generation Programme which is secondary occupation.
- All (100%) the respondents don't have regular work in the agriculture.
- It is observed from the table 3.16, 82% of the respondents are not having agriculture work because of drought.
- It is evidenced from the table 3.17, all (100%) the respondents are working 5-8 hours in a day.
- All the respondents feel that there is discrimination in workplace between men and women regarding time.
- Majority (95%) of the respondents says, this agriculture wages is not enough to meet out the family requirement.

Suggestions

- It is found that the women labourers got employment in agriculture for only one third of the total days in a year. The rest of the days they are unemployed. So steps should be taken to impart entrepreneurship training to the labourers in activities like mushroom cultivation,

food processing, dairying etc. This should be done with the coordinated efforts of government departments, NGOs, SHGs *etc.* This will help them to gain self-employment and good income.

- The women labourers had many suggestions to overcome the problem of unemployment during off season like proper implementation of employment guarantee programmes, higher wages in agriculture, training to improve skill and for starting entrepreneurship activities and provide loans without much formalities.
- Government must take proper step to reduce the exploitation of the unorganised workers.
- The government must take a policy decision to bring all the unorganised labourers under act to protect their interest.
- The problems of migrant labourers should be examined in detail by the Ministry of Agriculture.
- Work force is not aware of laws in force and facilities supposed to be provided by employers. Awareness programmes should, therefore, be organized regularly.
- Examination of the existing laws for women in the enforcement sector, i.e. agriculture sector and review the effectiveness or counter productivity of these legislations/laws for women in agriculture.

Conclusion

These workers, like farmers, are at the heart of the commercial food production system. Yet these working women and men remain largely invisible to policy and decision-makers in governments, agricultural and rural development agencies, intergovernmental organizations, science and research institutions, agricultural banks and credit institutions as well as in many civil society organizations and groups. They are hardly ever acknowledged in United Nations documentation outside of the ILO, or in rural development strategies. Successful sustainable development requires that both small farmers and waged workers are given considerably more attention as distinct groups, each with its own political, economic and social needs and contributions; that both groups figure in sustainable rural development strategies and programmes; and that more support is given to building and strengthening links between these groups in the interests of sustainable development and poverty eradication.

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